

EFFECTS OF HUMUS, ALBIT®, GARLIC AND WOOD ASH EXTRACTS ON THE GROWTH OF *Aspergillus flavus* AND ON SEED VIGOUR OF MAIZE (*Zea mays* L)

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to assess the antifungal activities of albit®, humus, garlic (*Allium sativum*) and wood ash aqueous extracts on maize seed-borne fungi with emphasis on *Aspergillus flavus*. Local and improved variety of maize seeds were obtained from Gwagwalada Abuja market. The treated seeds were inoculated on Petri dishes containing Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) in the Laboratory. Four seeds were placed on each media, replicated four times and kept in the incubator for 72 hrs. A pure isolate of *A. flavus* was prepared from the mixed culture on maize seed. The *A. flavus* was soaked in each of the treatments for 2 hrs, air-dried, sown and incubated in the PDA order to assess their effects on radial growth of *A. flavus*. The radial growth of *A. flavus* was observed at 2DAI, 3DAI and 5DAI. Another treated seeds were sown in the screen house of the Faculty of Agriculture to assess the germination percentage and seedling vigour of the seeds and phytotoxicity of the extracts. It was observed that at 72 Hours After Incubation (HAI) garlic extract applied seeds has no fungal growth while other treatments had varied radial growth. For the seeds of local and improved varieties of maize sown in the screen house, the germination percentage (77.80%) and seedling vigour (6.80) of seeds treated with humus were significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) than other treatments. Wood ash and humus extracts seed treatment were found to have enhanced the germination and seedling vigour of maize seeds but did not inhibit *A. flavus*. Though garlic extract treatment led to non-radial growth of *A. flavus*, it was however phytotoxic at high concentration as it inhibited maize seed germination and reduced seed vigour. Formulating the optimum concentration of garlic for seed treatment should be the next focus of research.

Keywords: *Aspergillus flavus*, Garlic, Extracts, Growth, Seed vigour, Maize

INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea mays* L) is widely grown around the world both in temperate and tropical regions, it is an annual crop and it is a major cereal grain grown in Nigeria for its high nutritional value (Peter *et al.*, 2014). During storage, several kinds of fungi can remain associated to maize seeds either causing their deterioration or simply remain viable to infect germinating seeding. The fungi genera typically found in stored grains are *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium* and some xerophytic species, several of them with capabilities of producing toxins (Castellari *et*

al., 2010). Seed fungi especially species of *Aspergillus*, *Diplodia*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, *Trichoderma* and a number of phycomycetes affect the seed of all forest species (Griffin, 2010). Maize seeds have been reported to be infected by *A. flavus* in the field prior to their harvest and in storage (Klueken *et al.*, 2009).

The rank of fungi is second after insects as the cause of deterioration and loss of maize (Uzma and Shahida, 2007). *A. flavus* becomes systemic and produces aflatoxin and livesces in seedling of maize and damage stored corn. Maize is also affected by milder

pathogen (Ahmed *et al.*, 2006). *Fusarium* invade more than 50% of maize grain before harvest and produce mycotoxin (Usma and Shahida 2007), while *A. flavus* is a food contaminant and capable of producing aflatoxin (Charity *et al.*, 2010). The losses caused by seed fungi may occur during seed development, storage or germination. Damage may result from loss of seed viability or from seedling infection following germination (Griffin, 2010). The control of maize disease is very important as a complementary technology to boost maize production. Tagne *et al.* (2008) reported that various approaches have been used over many decades to control maize diseases. These include breeding resistance varieties of maize, chemical treatment including seed treatment and biological control. Natural products of higher plants give a new source of antimicrobial agents with possible novel mechanism of action (Kaur and Kaur, 2010).

Aspergillus flavus is a common soil and seed-borne fungus that is primarily saprotrophic as it feeds on dead plant tissue, (Chang, 2014). *A. flavus* has the ability to generate secondary metabolites – the B aflatoxins which is a highly toxic carcinogen. It is also a food-borne fungus and one of the most common species identified on preserved foodstuffs, notably grains (Klich, 2007, Dobson, 2016).

Natural plant materials may be a viable alternative to commercial fungicides for protecting grains and other agricultural commodities from *A. flavus*-produced aflatoxin B₁ (Krishnamurthy, 2008; Kutawa, 2018). Garlic (*Allium sativum*) belongs to the family Amaryllidaceae and genus *Allium*. Garlic extract contain allicin which is the active ingredient responsible for its antifungal activity. Garlic extracts have been reported to inhibit the growth of pathogenic fungi (Daniel *et al.*, 2015; Kutawa *et al.*, 2018). Wood ash is a waste product obtained from the combustion of wood, it contains various

amounts of plant nutrients: Calcium, Magnesium, Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium, Sodium, Iron, Manganese, Copper, and Zinc absorbed by the plant during normal growth, their chemical composition varies widely depending on the nature of plant burnt, the plant part and intensity of burning (Nottidge and Nottidge, 2012). It has been proven that wood ash improves soil chemical properties, ear leaf nutrient composition, growth and grain yields of maize (Nottidge *et al.*, 2007). In agriculture, plant ashes are frequently used as mineral fertilizers. The fertilization value of ash depends on the type of combusted material and the type of wood (Ciesielczuk *et al.*, 2014).

King humus plus® is a soil conditioner and plant growth stimulant for all kinds of crops. The product is 100 % organic. It basically reduces fertilizer input by half and increases yield by 40%. It contains humic acid, potassium and organic materials for all kinds of crops. King humus plus is proven to increase root vitality, improve nutrient uptake, increase chlorophyll synthesis, help seed germination, increase fertilizer retention, stimulate beneficial microbial activity and promote healthier plants and improved yields according to the manufacturer.

Albit® is a plant growth stimulant of biological origin. It increases yield and protect the plant against pathogens. It is composed of poly-beta-hydroxybutyrate (6.2g PHB L⁻¹) and a balanced set of micro and macro elements and terpenes acids. It is proven that albit® increase seed vigour, germination rate in arable crops and has the potential to induce resistance to fungi as well as bacteria infections (Anjorin and Salako, 2010). This study aimed at assessing the effect of humus, albit®, woodash and garlic extracts on the growth of *A. flavus* and seed vigour of maize.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

This experiment was conducted at the laboratory of the Department of Crop Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Abuja.

Collection of sample

The maize grains; local and improved variety (Garin sarkin 90 days), garlic bulb and albit® were gotten from Gwagwalada market, Abuja; the wood ash was gotten from a restaurant in Gwagwalada and the humus was provided by the Vice-Chancellor of University of Abuja for efficacy testing.

Procedure of experimentation

Preparation and sterilization of media

The media was prepared using Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) according to the manufacturer's instructions, 19.5g of PDA was dissolved in 500ml of distilled water and then sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C and pressure of 15PSI for 15minutes. The media was allowed to cool to a temperature of 45-50°C and stayed for about 10minutes to solidify.

Preparation and application of treatments

The garlic bulbs were peeled and the axillary buds were weighed and washed with distilled water, 125g of garlic was blended with 250ml of distilled water and filtered with a sterile mesh cloth. Ten seeds of each variety were soaked in the filtrate for 2 hrs and air dried for 24 hrs to come back to its normal moisture level. The humus (king humus plus®) was prepared according to the manufacturer's instruction. 0.4g of humus was dissolved in 250 ml of distilled water and ten seeds of each variety were soaked in the diluted solution for 2 hrs and air-dried for 2 hrs.

Albit®, is composed of poly-beta-hydroxybutyrate and a balanced set of micro and macro elements and terpenes acids. The

liquid gel substance was thoroughly shaken and 10ml of albit® was diluted in 10ml of distilled water. Ten seeds of each variety were soaked in the solution for 2 hrs and air-dried for 2 hrs before used. One hundred and twentyfive grams (125g) of wood ash was dissolve with 250ml of distilled water and filtered with muslin cloth. Ten seeds of each variety were soaked in the filtrate for 2 hrs and air dried for 2 hrs before use.

Preparation of pure culture of fungal isolate

The younger *A. flavus* colony were aseptically picked from the mixed culture and transferred to fresh sterile PDA plates to obtain pure culture. The pure culture of PDA plate was placed in the incubator and grown at 27±2°C for 5days.

Inoculation of seed

The treated maize seeds were inoculated by placing them on Petri dishes containing the culture medium, three seeds were aseptically placed on each Petri dish and it was kept in the incubator at 27±1 for 72 hrs.

Identification of isolated fungi

At 72 hrs after inoculation, identification of the isolated fungi was done macroscopically. The identification was based on observed culture growth patterns, size, texture and mycelial colour in line with standard manual.

Treatment of *A. flavus* isolated from maize seeds

The *A. flavus* was soaked in all the treatments (humus, albit®, garlic and wood ash extracts) and positive control (fluconazole), for 0 hr, 2 hrs and 4 hrs respectively. Two drops of each treated *A. flavus* was applied on a fresh sterile PDA plates, it was then placed in the incubator for 5days and the radial growth was observed and measured at 48 hrs, 72 hrs and 120 hrs respectively.

Germination in the laboratory

Filter paper (Whatman® 1 cat no 1001 110) was placed on 30 petri dishes (9cm diameter) as a growth medium and it was moistened with 2 ml of distilled water, 4 treated seeds were placed in each of the Petri dishes and covered, each treatment and control were replicated four times in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) for the local and improved maize varieties. One milliliter (1ml) of distilled water was applied when necessary.

Germination in the screen house

A set of three seeds were sown per plot, garden soil was collected behind Faculty of Agriculture were steam sterilized and used as growth medium. A total of 30 polythene bags were each filled with the sterile soil and placed in the Faculty of Agriculture screen house. The soil was moistened with water before the treated seeds and the control (applied with distilled water) were sown at a depth of 2 cm.

Parameter measured

Germination percentage: The emergence of a radicle was used as the criterion for germination in the laboratory and screen house. Germination count was obtained 3days after sowing by counting the numbers of germinated seeds and expressed mathematically in percentage.

$$\text{Germination \%} = \frac{x_2}{x_1} \times 100$$

Where X2 = Number of germinated seeds

X1 = Total number of seeds planted

Seedling vigour index in the laboratory:

The seedling vigour index for the data collected in the laboratory was expressed mathematically as:

$$\text{Seedling vigour index (SVI)} = \frac{GP (PL + RL)}{1000}$$

Where GP = Germination percentage (%)

PL = Mean plumule length (mm)

RL = Mean radicle length (mm)

Shoot length, leaf width and length

The shoot length, leaf length and leaf width was taken at first, second, third and fourth week in the screen house. At the fourth week, the plants were uprooted to measure root length and it was dried for 10 days, then the root and shoot biomass was taken with a weighing balance.

Seedling vigour index in the screen house:

The percentage seedling vigour index for the data collected in the screen house was expressed mathematically as:

$$\text{Seedling vigour index (SVI)} = \frac{SE (SL + RL)}{1000}$$

Where SE = Seedling emergence percentage

SL= Mean shoot length (mm)

RL= Mean root length (mm)

Leaf area:

The leaf area was computed as:

Leaf Area = L x B x alpha
Where L = mean length of the leaf area (cm),

B = mean breadth of the leaf area

Alpha = 0.75 (Rasheedat Ajala *et al.*, 2017).

Root and shoot biomass: The root and shoot biomass (dry matter) yield per plant (g) was determined by harvesting the plants at 28 DAS and air-dried until a constant weight is observed. The biomass was taken with a weighing balance (Rasheedat Ajala *et al.*, 2017).

Radial growth: For the treated *Aspergillus flavus*, the radial growth was used as the criterion for the most effective treatment; the radial growth was measured at 48hours, 72hours and 120hours with a transparent plastic ruler. The measurement was taken in millimeter (mm).

Statistical analysis

Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and treatment means were subjected to Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) ($p < 0.05$) using SPSS version 20 package.

Plate 1 Presence of *Rhizopus* spp on maize seeds treated with humic extract at 72 HAS

RESULTS

Effects of treatments (humus, albit®, garlic and wood ash extracts) on maize seed-borne fungi

The major fungal pathogens found on the maize seed sample selected for treatment are *Fusarium* spp(50%), *Aspergillus flavus*(50%), *Aspergillus niger*(25%), *Aspergillus terreus* (50%) and *Penicillium* spp (6.25%).

Effects of humus on maize seed-borne fungi

Maize seeds treated with humus germinated on all the plots at 48 hrs. At 72 hrs, there was incidence of *Fusarium* spp and *Rhizopus* spp on all the seeds of local and improved varieties(Figs1 and 2) . This indicated that humus was not effective against seed borne fungi of the seeds.

Plate 2 Presence of *Fusarium* spp on maize seeds treated with humic extract 72HAS

Effects of albit® on maize seed borne fungi

At 48 hrs, seeds treated with albit® have fungi growth in all the plots sown with the two varieties. For the local variety, at 72 hrs the 25.0% had no incidence of fungal growth; 75.0% of the plots showed the incidence of *Fusarium* spp and *A. niger* while 25.0% had

A. flavus, *A. niger* and *Fusarium* spp.(Figs 3 and 4) For the improved variety, 25.0% of the plots had *A. flavus* and *Fusarium* spp; 325.0% had no any fungi growth while while the remaining 25.0% had *A. flavus*, *A.niger* and *Fusarium* spp. There was indication that albit® was slightly effective against seed-borne fungi of maize seeds.

Plate 3 Presence of *A. flavus*, *A.niger* and *Fusarium* spp at 48 HAS on maize seeds treated with albit

Effects of garlic extract on maize seed-borne fungi

All the seeds treated with garlic extract did not have any growth at 48 and at 72 HAS. Garlic extract was observed to be fungicidal against seed borne mycobiota.

Effects of wood ash extract on maize seed borne fungi

The seeds treated with wood ash extract have growth at 48 hrs. At 72 hrs, 25.0% of the local

Plate 5 Showing the presence of *A.niger*, *A.flavus* and *Fusarium* at 48 HAS on maize seeds treated with wood ash extract

Germination in the laboratory

Effects of the treatments (humus, albit®, garlic and wood ash extracts) on germination percentage and seedling vigour of local variety of maize grown on Petri dishes

Table1 shows the local variety of maize grown on Petri dishes. Among other

Plate 4 Presence of *A. flavus*, *A.niger* and *Fusarium* spp on maize seeds treated with albit

variety has *A.niger*, *A.flavus* and *Fusarium* incidence, one fourth (25.0%) had only *Fusarium* spp and the remaining 50% had incidence of *A. flavus* and *A.niger* (Figs. 5 and 6). For the improved variety, 25.0% had incidence of *A.flavus* , *A.niger*. *Penicillium* spp, *Fusarium* spp. And other 75.0% showed only *A. niger* . Wood ash extract had no much effect against maize seed borne fungi

Plate 6 Showing the presence of *A.flavus*, *A.niger*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* at 72 HAS on maize seeds treated with wood ash extract

treatments, the germination percentage for humus is significantly different ($p < 0.05$) as compared with the control; it has the highest germination percentage with 77.80%; this shows that it has effect on germination rate. Also seedling vigour for humus (6.80) is significantly different ($p < 0.05$) as compared with the control (4.56).

Table 1: Germination percentage and seedling vigour of local variety of maize grown on Petri dishes

S/N	TRTS	PL2DAS	PL3DAS	PL4DAS	PL5DAS	RL2DAS	RL3DAS	RL4DAS	RL5DAS	GERM% 3DAS	S.VIGOUR 5DAS
1	Wood ash	0.00 ^a	22.67 ^{ab}	29.17 ^{ab}	31.33 ^{ab}	0.00 ^a	24.33 ^{abc}	27.67 ^{ab}	31.00 ^{ab}	33.33 ^{ab}	2.04 ^a
2	Albit®	0.00 ^a	1.33 ^a	2.67 ^b	3.33 ^a	0.00 ^a	2.67 ^a	5.00 ^a	6.00 ^a	11.10 ^a	0.18 ^a
3	Humus	5.93 ^b	42.33 ^b	46.77 ^a	49.83 ^b	5.67 ^b	58.07 ^c	65.23 ^b	69.00 ^b	77.80 ^b	6.80 ^b
4	Garlic	0.00 ^a	17.00 ^{ab}	21.50 ^{ab}	31.17 ^{ab}	0.00 ^a	16.17 ^{ab}	20.17 ^a	28.17 ^{ab}	44.43 ^{ab}	1.78 ^a
5	Control	7.50 ^b	40.53 ^b	46.77 ^b	48.50 ^b	5.27 ^b	38.87 ^{bc}	44.60 ^{ab}	46.37 ^{ab}	66.67 ^a	6 ^{ab}

Treatment means followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 5% level of probability.

Effects of the treatments (humus, albit®, garlic and wood ash extracts) on germination percentage and seedling vigour of improved variety of maize grown on Petri dishes

Table 2 shows the improved variety of maize grown on Petri dishes. Seeds treated with garlic extract and albit® did not germinate; the germination percentage for humus and wood ash extract are significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than other treatments, wood ash extract has germination percentage of 69.10% while humus has 73.33% which is lower than the control (66.67%). Also seedling vigour for humus (3.38) and wood ash extract (3.14) are significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than the control (2.94); this shows that humus and wood ash extract has positive effect on the seeds.

Germination in the screen house

Effects of the treatments (humus, albit®, garlic and wood ash extracts) on germination percentage and seedling vigour of local variety of maize grown in the screen house

Table 3 shows the local variety of maize grown in screen house. The shoot biomass, root length and leaf area for all the treatments are not significantly different from each other; the root biomass of albit®(2.17) is significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from other treatments as compared with the control(1.93); the seedling emergence percentage for wood ash(91.67%) is significantly different ($p < 0.05$) among others as compared with the control(75%), also the seedling vigour for wood ash extract (79.33) is significantly different ($p < 0.05$) as compared with the control(19.00). This shows that wood ash extract has effect on the seedling emergence and vigour of maize seeds.

Table 2: Germination percentage and seedling vigour of improved variety of maize grown on Petri dishes

S/N	TRTS	PL3DAS	PL4DAS	PL5DAS	RL3DAS	RL4DAS	RL5DAS	Germ% 3DAS	S.VIGOUR 5DAS
1	Woodash	5.00 ^a	5.00 ^a	6.67 ^a	5.00 ^a	10.00 ^{ab}	13.33 ^{ab}	69.10 ^a	3.14 ^a
2	Albit®	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a
3	Humus	12.00 ^a	14.17 ^{ab}	19.67 ^{ab}	31.00 ^b	33.33 ^b	40.00 ^b	73.33 ^{ab}	3.38 ^{ab}
4	Garlic	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a
5	Control	36.67 ^b	31.67 ^b	34.67 ^b	19.43 ^{ab}	24.77 ^{ab}	29.00 ^{ab}	66.67 ^b	2.94 ^b

Treatment means followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 5% level of probability.

Table 3: Assessment of seedling emergence percentage and seedling vigour of local variety of maize grown in screen house

S/N	TRTS	SL 1WAS	SL 2WAS	SL 3WAS	SL 4WAS	S. Biomass	Root Biomass	Root Length	Leaf Area	S.EMER (%)	S.VIGOU R
1	Wood ash	35.93 ^b	83.67	100.87	120.27	1.13	2.02 ^{ab}	238.67	3548.67	91.67 ^b	79.33 ^b
2	Albit®	30.67 ^{ab}	86.00	118.17	138.10	1.21	2.17 ^b	197.67	4323.07	75.00 ^{ab}	21.20 ^{ab}
3	Humus	34.33 ^b	107.00	109.67	140.57	1.77	1.52 ^{ab}	259.33	4522.70	58.33 ^{ab}	16.30 ^a
4	Gartic	25.00 ^a	86.67	112.17	153.00	1.48	0.90 ^a	310.00	4382.53	33.33 ^a	13.90 ^a
5	Control	28.77 ^{ab}	87.53	108.10	140.00	1.19	1.93 ^{ab}	151.33	4903.20	75.00 ^{ab}	19.00 ^{ab}

Treatment means followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 5% level of probability.

Effects of the treatments (humus, albit®, garlic and wood ash extracts) on germination percentage and seedling vigour of improved variety of maize grown in the screen house

Table 4 shows the improved variety of maize grown in screen house. The seeds treated with garlic did not germinate. The shoot biomass of all the treatments are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from each other as compared with the control but does not have any effect on the shoot biomass, the root biomass of humus (2.53) is significantly different ($p < 0.05$) as compared with the control (1.39) which shows that humus has effect on the root biomass, the root length of humus (283.67) is different ($p < 0.05$) as compared with other treatments, the leaf area for all the treatments are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from each other as compared with the control, the seedling emergence percentage of all the treatments are not significantly different as compared

with the control, the seedling vigour of humus (15.68) and seedling emergence percentage of humus (55.69%) is significantly different from other treatments. This shows that humus has effect on the seedling vigour and seedling emergence percentage of the seed.

Effects of the treatments on radial growth of treated *A.flavus* isolated from maize seeds

A.flavus was soaked in each of the treatments for 0hrs, 2 hrs and 4hrs respectively. At 2DAI garlic does not have any growth of *A.flavus* as compared with the positive control; while other treatments has radial growth of *A.flavus* respectively; there is a significant different ($p < 0.05$) between garlic and other treatments (Table 5). At 3DAI it was observed that garlic inhibit the growth of *A.flavus* and also at 5DAI garlic extract is significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from other treatments as compared with the positive control as shown in Table 5 below.

Table 4: Assessment of seedling emergence percentage and seedling vigour of improved variety of maize grown in screen house

S/N	TRTS	SL			S. Biomass	Root Biomass	Root Length	LEAF AREA	S.EMER	S.VIGOUR	
		1WAS	2WAS	3WAS							4WAS
1	Wood ash	11.00 ^{ab}	31.10 ^a	39.29 ^a	42.33 ^a	0.33 ^a	0.92 ^{ab}	73.67 ^{ab}	1490.33 ^{ab}	25.00	7.83 ^{ab}
2	Albit®	11.00 ^{ab}	27.67 ^a	35.00 ^a	40.00 ^a	0.47 ^{ab}	0.23 ^a	100.00 ^{ab}	1586.10 ^{ab}	8.33	3.20 ^{ab}
3	Humus	32.17 ^{bc}	97.00 ^b	118.00 ^b	141.00 ^b	1.37 ^{bc}	2.53 ^b	283.67 ^b	3889.87 ^{bc}	55.69	15.68 ^a
4	Garlic	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00	0.00 ^a
5	Control	36.73 ^c	94.23 ^b	119.73 ^b	147.77 ^b	1.42 ^c	1.39 ^{ab}	280.67 ^b	5309.87 ^c	41.67	14.10 ^{ab}

Treatment means followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 5% level of probability

Table 5: Radial growth of treated *A.flavus* isolated from maize seeds

S/N	TRTS	0H2DAI	2H2DAI	4H2DAI	0H3DAI	2H3DAI	4H3DAI	0H5DAI	2H5DAI	4H5DAI
1	Wood ash	45.00 ^c	41.67 ^c	40.67 ^c	41.67 ^b	41.00 ^b	40.33 ^b	43.33 ^b	45.00 ^b	45.00 ^b
2	Albit®	21.00 ^b	33.33 ^b	29.33 ^b	33.33 ^b	37.00 ^b	39.00 ^b	43.33 ^b	42.67 ^b	39.33 ^b
3	Humus	41.00 ^c	34.67 ^b	38.67 ^c	40.00 ^b	37.00 ^b	41.00 ^b	41.67 ^b	44.00 ^b	44.33 ^b
4	Garlic	0.00 ^a	4.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	6.00 ^a				
5	+ve control	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	3.00 ^a	3.33 ^a	0.00 ^a	7.00 ^a	7.67 ^a	0.00 ^a

Treatment means followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 5% level of probability.

DISCUSSION

From this study *Fusarium* spp, *A. flavus*, *A.niger*, *A. terrreus* and *Penicillium* spp were found associated with maize seeds. This result agreed with the findings by Anjorin *et al.*(2013) who reported that *A. flavus*, *Fusarium* spp, *A.niger*, and *Rhizopus stolonifer* were associated with maize seeds. Garlic extracts was found highly effective against the fungi pathogens, the inhibitory effect of the extract was high on *A.flavus* at different hours of soaking (0hr, 2hrs and 4hrs). Similar findings on the antifungal properties of garlic extract against other common fungal pathogens have been reported by Abdulaziz *et al.* (2018). Most of the maize seeds treated with garlic extracts did not germinate; few that germinated have very low seedling vigour. This disagree with the findings by Analia *et al.* (2013) who reported that seeds treated with garlic extract at ratio 1:10 had a relatively better germination percentage, plumule and radicle length, and seedlings vigour.

Wood ash extracts has the highest germination percentage and seedling vigour, this agree with Moyinjesu (2010) who reported that soaking seeds in wood ash extract encourage their photosynthetic capability, good growth and yield of the crops.

Wood ash extract does not have any effects on seed borne pathogenic fungi; it have a very high radial growth of *A. flavus*. This disagree with the findings by Oguntade and Adekunle (2010) that wood-ash of *Nauclea diderrichii* and *Piptadeniastrum africanum* were found to inhibit the growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *A.niger*, *A. flavus*, *A. fumigatus*, *Rhizopus* and *Macrophomina* spp. Humus (King humus plus) is an organic soil conditioner

and growth stimulant. It helps in strengthen root vitality, promote quicker seed germination, enhance production and crop appearance according to the manufacturer specifications. From this study, humus does not have any effects on the radial growth of *A.flavus* but seeds treated with humus have good germination percentage and seedling vigour. Albit® does not have effects on the radial growth of *A.flavus* which means it does not have antifungicidal properties, also the germination percentage and seedling vigour of the maize seeds is very low. Anjorin and Salako (2010) reported that albit® increase seed vigour, germination rate in arable crops and has the potential to induce resistance to fungi as well as bacterial infections, in order to obtain the desired seed germination and vigour from Albit® application, the concentration of Albit® is a major factor. The optimal range of concentration for the biochemical presoaking should be between 0.2 - 0.4 ml L⁻¹ H₂O depending on the nature of the seed.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that the use of botanical such as garlic extract for seed treatment is effective against seed borne fungi pathogens especially *A. flavus*. Also it was found that the use of organic substance such as wood ash extracts and humus were effective solutions for germination and seedling vigour of maize seeds rather than been fungicidal. If maize seeds are treated with garlic extract at high concentration, the seeds might experience low germination percentage and seedling vigour, due to phytotoxic potential of garlic. Thus optimum concentration of garlic should always be applied as seed treatment.

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